

Supporting material

Peptide-based biosensor for real-time monitoring of protease biomarker activity using multi-parametric surface plasmon resonance spectroscopy

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S1. Biosensing Strategy

Fig. S1. Scheme of the peptide-based MMP-9 sensing strategy. First, the Au surface is coated linker molecules (Lipoic acid–PEG–Maleimide). Second, Au modified with linker is coupled to the substrate peptide via maleimide–thiol coupling. Finally, the peptide is exposed to a continuous flow of MMP-9. The entire process is performed in a continuous flow system at 30 °C. Upon exposure to MMP-9, the target peptides (peptide I and peptide II) gets cleaved at a specific site, whereas the control peptide (peptide III) without containing MMP-9 specific site is not cleaved by MMP-9. The SPR signal change before and after exposure to MMP-9 are compared.

S2. Peptide Synthesis

The peptides were manually synthesized on Rink Amid AM resin (0.34 mmol) using standard fluorenylmethoxycarbonyl (Fmoc)- SPPS. A 12 mL polypropylene syringe equipped with a frit was loaded with 500 mg of Ring Amide AM resin (loading capacity 0.68 mmol) and pre-swelled in DCM for 2 x 30 min. The Fmoc-deprotection was performed using 20% piperidine in DMF for 1 h. After draining the solution, the resin was washed with DMF 3 x 5 mL, DCM 3 x 5 mL and DMF 3 x 5 mL, respectively. The amino acid coupling was performed as a double coupling (2 x 1 h) using a solution of amino acid (3 equiv.) in DMF containing DIPEA (9 equiv.) and HATU (3 equiv.). After draining the solution and washing the resin, a capping step was performed using a solution of acetic anhydride:DIPEA:DCM (3:2:3) for 1 h. Each subsequent amino acid loading was conducted according to the procedures for Fmoc-deprotection, washing and amino acid coupling as previously described. For proline, a mixture of NMP: DMF (2:3) was used as solvent. The quencher (3 equiv.) was either coupled on the resin with DIPEA (9 equiv.) and HATU (3 equiv.) in DMF (building block (((2,4-dinitrophenyl)amino)propanoic acid)) or as a S_N-reaction using Sanger reagent (3 equiv.) with DIPEA (6 equiv.) in DMF for 2 x 2 h. The final peptide was cleaved from the resin (2 h) using either the cleavage cocktail with TFA: TIPS: H₂O (90:5:5) or TFA: H₂O: EDT: TIPS (90:4:4:2). The remaining resin was washed with TFA and DCM (5 mL) and the combined eluates were concentrated under reduced pressure at 40 °C. The obtained residue was precipitated in cold ether, centrifuged and purified by RP-HPLC using a gradient of 0.1% HCOOH in H₂O/ACN. The structures of peptides are shown in section 2.2 of the manuscript.

Fig. 2. Structure of building block (((2,4-dinitrophenyl)amino)propanoic acid).

According to a procedure of Bray et al. (Bray et al., 1991). To a solution of β -alanine (500 mg, 5.61 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) in 10% aqueous Na₂CO₃-solution (17 mL) was added dropwise a solution of 2,4-dinitrofluorobenzene (1149 mg, 6.17 mmol, 1.1 equiv.) in 1,4-dioxane (10 mL). The reaction was stirred at rt for 48 h and was then quenched with 10% citric acid (20 mL). The aqueous solution was extracted with EtOAc (3 x 20 mL) and the combined organic layers were washed with 10% citric acid:brine (1:1, 3 x 20 mL) and brine (3 x 20 mL). The organic layer was dried over Na₂SO₄, and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure at 40 °C. The residue was washed several times with diethyl ether to obtain the final residue as a yellow solid (1126 mg, 4.80 mmol, 86%). ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ / ppm = 8.88 (t, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 8.82 (d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H), 8.23 (dd, *J* = 9.6, 2.8 Hz, 1H), 7.26 (d, *J* = 9.7 Hz, 1H), 3.69 (q, *J* = 6.5 Hz, 2H), 2.65 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz,

2H). ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d_6): δ / ppm = 172.8, 148.0, 134.9, 130.1, 129.8, 123.6, 115.2, 32.9. mp: 144–146 °C; FT-IR: ν / cm^{-1} = 3353, 2946, 1693, 1615, 1583, 1519, 1419, 1232, 1128, 1057, 922, 831, 744, 705.

S3. Michaelis-Menten enzyme kinetics of MMP-9 with peptide III

Michaelis-Menten plot

Fig. S3. Michaelis-Menten enzyme kinetics of MMP-9 with peptide III.

S4. Spectra of (((2,4-dinitrophenyl)amino)propanoic acid)

Fig. S4. ^1H NMR of ((2,4-dinitrophenyl)amino)propanoic acid.

S5. Spectra of (((2,4-dinitrophenyl)amino)propanoic acid)

Fig. S5. ¹³C NMR of (((2,4-dinitrophenyl)amino)propanoic acid).

S6. LCMS Chromatogram of Peptide I

Fig. S6. LCMS chromatogram of peptide I at 254 nm.

S7. LCMS Chromatogram of Peptide II

Fig. S7. LCMS chromatogram of peptide II at 254 nm.

S8. LCMS Chromatogram of Peptide III

Fig. S8. LCMS chromatogram of peptide III at 254 nm.

S9. LCMS Chromatogram of Peptide IV

Fig. S9. LCMS chromatogram of peptide IV at 254 nm.

S10. Investigation of Non-Specific Interaction of MMP-9 using MP-SPR

Fig. S10. a) SPR response (at 670 nm) due to non-specific interaction of MMP-9 with Au (shown in black), Au modified with PEG-based linker molecules (450 μ M) (shown in red), and Au functionalized with a combination of linker (450 μ M) and peptide III (195 μ M) (shown in blue). 1 nM MMP-9 solution was continuously injected on different surfaces (20 min, 10 μ L/min) and finally washed with PBS (10 min, 40 μ L/min). b) Represents a summary of end SPR response obtained at approx. 10 mins after washing with PBS. The entire measurement was carried out at 30 $^{\circ}$ C and at pH = 7.4. MMP-9 binds significantly less on Au passivated with a specific combination of linker and peptide.

To evaluate the non-specific binding, 1 nM MMP-9 solution diluted in PBS (pH = 7.4) was introduced on bare Au, Au coated with linker molecules (Lipoic acid-PEG-Maleimide), and peptide III immobilized on linker modified Au (20 min, 10 uL/min) followed by the washing step with PBS (10 min, 10 uL/min) and the SPR end responses obtained after 10 min were compared (Fig. S10 (a)). MMP-9 was first infused directly on the bare Au surface followed by its exposure to Au coated with linker molecules, and on Au modified with a combination of linker and peptide III. The direct exposure of MMP-9 on Au results in a maximum binding response of 0.017 Deg (Fig. S10 (b)). The initial increase in the response upon MMP-9 injection is due to the combined effect resulting from the bulk effect of glycerol present in sample solution and MMP-9 interaction. The binding of MMP-9 is significantly reduced to 0.006 Deg on Au modified with PEG-based linker molecule. This could be due to the fact that PEGs linkers not only passivate Au but also have anti-fouling properties (Gupta et al., 2015; Shin et al., 2013; Sun et al., 2020). The weakest binding signal of MMP-9 with a shift of 0.002 Deg results from its interaction with Au functionalized with a specific combination of linker and peptide III.

S11. Blank Measurement on Peptide II in Buffer and Cell Culture Medium (RPMI-1640)

Fig. S11. Investigation of the sensitivity of the sensor. Blank measurements were performed by infusing buffer (PBS) and RPMI (RPMI containing 10 mM HEPES) solutions (each for 20 mins, 10 ul/min) without containing MMP-9 on peptide II and finally washing with buffer (in PBS, 20 mins, 40 ul/min). The detail of peptide surface fabrication is given in section 2.7 of the manuscript. The error bar represents the standard deviation of three data set. The measurement was carried out at 30 °C and at pH = 7.4.

S12. Estimation of Limit of Detection of the Sensor in Buffer and Cell-Culture Medium

Fig. S12. Estimation of Limit of Detection, a) in buffer selecting a linear detection range between 5 pM – 9 nM MMP-9 concentrations, b) and in cell culture medium (RPMI-1640) within a linear range between 20 pM – 3 nM MMP-9 concentrations. The LOD of the sensor in % was calculated using equation 2 described in section 3.3 of the manuscript. Solid blue lines show the calculated LOD (in %) in buffer and RPMI. The point of intersection between the linearly fitted curve (black solid lines) and the LOD in % gives us the LOD in molar concentration.

S13. Bulk Effect of Glycerol in SPR Measurements

Fig. S13. Injection of buffer containing glycerol on linker modified Au surface functionalized with peptide II. Three data set is presented in the figure. During solution injection, SPR signal is changed by approx. 0.044 Deg due to the bulk effect of glycerol which is finally removed during washing the surface with buffer alone.

References

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